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Choosing and implementing persistent identifiers

Guide for research organisations

Finnish Open Science Coordination
Working group for linking and citing data 2020

Content

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- Identifiers in research information
- Benefits of using identifiers for information management, research and science
- Deployment of persistent identifiers
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How research organisations can make their research information management more efficient and support the FAIR principles by using persistent identifiers.

Information kit for experts

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Identifiers in
research
information

Identifiers and research information

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This document is a deliverable of the Working group for linking and citing data within the Finnish Open Science Coordination in 2020

The aim is to offer research organisations support for deployment of persistent identifiers by offering information about:

- benefits of using identifiers
- considerations in choosing and implementing persistent identifiers
- available persistent identifiers

Unique and persistent identifiers enable efficient and reliable linking of research information

Definition of a persistent identifier (PID)

A persistent identifier (PID) is:

- **unique**; it is never used again
- **persistent**; the same object is never given a new identifier within the same system
- **functional**; there are services attached to the identifier

A PID is owned by an organisation that is responsible for maintaining it

Allocating PIDs is governed by rules

ARK, DOI, Handle and URN are PID systems. Only the three last mentioned are used in Finland.

The PID services are based on **resolver services**, that contain metadata about the PIDs

The application of PID systems is governed by standards and national and international organisations like the DOI Foundation, DOI Registration Agencies and their partners like CSC and the Federation of Learned Societies.

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PID structure

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A **DOI** contains a prefix, a suffix and a slash (/) between the two. The combination of prefix and suffix is unique and persistent, and must never be used again. A prefix is never reused for a different registrant and a registrant must never reuse a suffix for another object.

The DOI resolver proxy address <https://doi.org> is added in front of the DOI.

Ex: <https://doi.org/10.23978/inf.98302>

A **URN** contains three parts:

- the string urn:
- the identifier of the namespace, i.e. nbn:
- the identifier that is unique within the namespace

Each namespace (n = 50) has its own rules regarding the object that is identified and how the identifier is structured

The resolver address is added in front of the URN, i.e. <http://urn.fi>

Ex: <http://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:fsd:T-FSD3424>

Other identifiers

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Systems that don't use resolver applications offer other types of identifiers. They can be based on international standards, *de facto* standards or might be local solutions.

To be functional, identifiers are represented as URIs, i.e.

<https://isni.org/isni/0000000404505858>

Examples

- Identifiers for agents, like ORCID and ISNI
- Identifiers in geographic information systems
- ISBN identifiers for books
- Accession numbers in data archives, i.e.:
 - NP_999856.1 (protein)
 - rs141296055 (mutation)

A **Cool URI** is a web link, that is always (re)directed to the same resource, even when the location has changed.

Cool URIs as identifiers

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Cool URIs are identifiers that have to be kept functional using HTTP redirect if the location of the resource or landing page is changed.

In practice it has become evident that this method is intricate in the long run and the functionalities are limited, for instance, regarding linking to parallel locations.

Over time using Cool URIs in a persistent way is expensive and offers comparably few technical functionalities.

Cool URIs are prone to link rot (404 errors) and content drift, e.g. the object (re)presented can change without warning or documentation.

This has been shown in studies, see i.e. these articles:

- <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0115253>
- <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0167475>

No similar large studies exist regarding PIDs.

The benefits of using PIDs for organisational information management

- PIDs enhance information management and accessibility
 - A resource might have many locations and addresses which can change over time, while the PID is unique
 - A PID can offer more services and functionalities than a URL (i.e. the PID can be linked to several copies)
- PIDs build interoperability and support linking across systems
 - Information can be stored only in one system as the PID can be used for reliable referencing between services
 - The semantics and original context of the information can be maintained
- PIDs support data policy implementation and efficient information management planning
 - Using PIDs directs towards using common authority data (semantic artefacts like ontologies and global standards names for agents)

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Other benefits

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Data citation gives visibility and enhances the usability of datasets

- PIDs can enable unambiguous references even to single variables or subsets
- functional and reliable citations are useful both for the researcher and the research organisation
- persistent references enable creation of rich data stores and graphs

Altmetrics (visibility of publications on the web and in social media)

- DOI or other PIDs offer good links when posting about outputs
- using DOI makes it possible to get information about social media impact for instance from the Altmetric.com service
- information about altmetrics can be presented as an indicator of societal relevance when making funding applications
- a mention in social media can lead to new scientific cooperation

International interoperability

- many international publishers and services offer DOIs and require author identifiers like ORCID

Benefits of PIDs for researchers

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- Enhanced findability for research information
- Efficient use of research information benefits the researcher by
 - easier and better citation
 - simplifies funding application
 - supporting quicker submission of research outputs
 - enabling easy demonstration of good research management
 - enabling simple and early data sharing, e.g. as “nanopublications”¹
- Supports open science and open peer review
- Enables unambiguous citation
- Supports implementing the FAIR data principles, as “the PID is included in the metadata”

¹ http://nanopub.org/wordpress/?page_id=65

Benefits of PIDs for science

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- Strengthens reproducibility
- Enhances data and information provenance tracing and documentation
- Research data and metadata management and the lifecycle management and dissemination of both become better and more efficient
- Better visibility creates opportunities for more diverse data and information use across domains
- The impact of research grows
 - facilitates tracking and impact assessment
- Supports responsible evaluation
 - for instance open access status can be checked using the DOIIn (see <https://unpaywall.org/>, not complete information)

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Deployment of
persistent
identifiers

1. Landscape analysis

- Define objects to identify
- Identify relevant practices, standards and regulations
- Map external information systems and services
- Analyse the current state and the target state of your organisation

2. Comparing alternatives

- Assess the different PID systems and services for each object type
- Compare costs
- Plan for the life cycle
- Assess the trustworthiness of the solutions

3. Deployment and maintenance

- Create policies, guidelines and documentation
- Implement and offer training

Landscape analysis

Define objects to identify

Find out which kinds of things need identifiers and which is the relevant context for each case. Is there a need to have unique identifiers for people, organisations, research outputs, projects, files, datasets and so on? Do the identifiers have to be unique locally or globally, also outside the own information systems? How persistent do should they be?

Landscape analysis

Identify relevant practices, standards and regulations

Every user and stakeholder group have their own requirements and practices.

If you allocate identifiers for research data, be clear about the domain specific requirements and practices. It might also be necessary to take into account regulations regarding identifiers stemming from the government, laws or long term preservation requirements.

Notice, that for instance publications already have identifiers like the ISBN that can be turned into a PID (i.g. URN:ISBN)

Landscape analysis

Map external information systems and services

Find out the requirements of interfacing services and systems like Journal.fi, Fairdata.fi, OpenAIRE, Digital preservation for research data, digitalpreservation.fi, Minedu data collection etc.

For which things do these require identifiers or PIDs and what are they like?
Find out which PID services are available and how they are used by other research organisations and infrastructures.

Landscape analysis

Analyse the current state and the target state of your organisation

Look at the needs of your organisation and the opportunities that are available.

Which is the target state?

What kind of identifiers and services are already in use?

What are the capabilities to use and manage PIDs and PID services? Do you have relevant strategic goals, a data policy or a data management policy?

What kind of service level agreements are required in different cases?

Comparing alternatives

Assess the different PID systems and services for each object type

- Scope: Is the identifier suitable for this type of objects?
- Technology: Is the technology suitable for the use case and compatible with the organisation architecture? Which metadata are involved and where are they stored? Is the availability sufficient?
- Management: how is the administration and maintenance of the identifiers organised? Who is responsible for resolving and metadata curation?

Comparing alternatives

Compare costs

Evaluate the costs, because there are always costs involved. A published PID is a promise, that has significance for a long time.

- Fees: some identifiers require paying membership fees and others are services you can buy
- Deployment: putting up an own Handle server has some costs, as has an API needed for URN
- Operations: all information systems have administrative and maintenance costs

Comparing alternatives

Plan for the life cycle

Plan for how the (persistent) identifiers can be managed in the long run, for instance when information systems are updated or you want to switch service provider. Is it possible to migrate the data or change the ownership of the identifier? Will the identified resources or services be discontinued or retired some day in the future?

Comparing alternatives

Assess the trustworthiness of the solutions

Technology: Is the technology based on open and well documented source code?

Governance: Who manages the schema, documentation and possible standards or APIs? Are governance and funding sustainable?
Who can influence future development and how can it be done?

Deployment and maintenance

Create policies, guidelines and documentation

Negotiate and enter the needed agreements. Describe principles of use in a PID policy and document ownership, practices and related processes for each identifier type.

Agree and document responsibilities for each PID type and service. Ensure management and findability of the documentation; this is useful both for sustainability and for audits.

Deployment and maintenance

Implement and offer training

Technical development should be done according the practices of the organisation. APIs are usually required at least for resolver services. Metadata management and updates should be done as user friendly and as automated as possible.

Use automatic validation whenever possible.

If your organisation is responsible for the storage of data objects ensuring integrity of the content is important.

Provide training and information about the services.

About costs

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There is no such thing as a free PID service. Even if you can get one for free, maintenance always carries some costs sooner or later.

The DOI fees are used to offer technical infrastructure for the DOI services.

The Handle and URN systems are free, but you have to provide resolver services yourself.

PID implementation requires knowledge of the system at hand.

DataCite Finland offers its members DOIs for research data. The consortium policy requires that the member organisation can ensure data integrity or at least provide a landing page that contains the master metadata of the dataset. CSC is the consortium lead.

The National Library of Finland currently offers URN services for free. These identifiers are used to identify publications and research datasets, among other things.

A published PID
is a promise

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Read more about identifiers in Finland: <https://wiki.eduuni.fi/x/V7qKCg>

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